

INFLUENCE OF POWER ULTRASONIC ON THE IMPREGNATION OF UNIDIRECTIONAL FIBERS IN CLOSED INJECTION PULTRUSION

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ABSTRACT

The influence of power ultrasonic (US) on the closed injection pultrusion is investigated in a real test environment. For this purpose, the US is directly integrated into the impregnation chamber of a pultrusion die. The chamber geometry is designed according to the patent of Koppernaes et al. A pure unidirectional reinforcement of glas fibers (SE 3030, 4800 tex, 3B, Belgium) and carbon fibers (C T50-4.0/240-E100, SGL Carbon SE, Germany) is used as laminate structure in combination with an epoxy resin system (Biresin® CR141, Sika, Germany). Additional temperature control channels are integrated into the impregnation chamber in order to extract the temperature's influence.

The following variables are investigated: Ultrasonic amplitude, position of US-coupling and temperature. Mechanical parameters (3-point bending, ILSS) are determined and macroscopic images are examined.

The investigation indicates that US can slightly increase the mechanical parameters. However, the same effect is achieved when tempering the impregnation system. Therefore, the effect of viscosity reduction is solely due to the temperature increase. The coupled power's upper limit is determined by the fiber, not the matrix. An acoustic sonication of the fibers with an US amplitude too high destroys the fibers.

In summary, US has a positive influence on the impregnation performance during pultrusion. However, the effect can be directly attributed to the resulting temperature increase of the matrix. Instead of excitation via US, a similar effect can also be achieved by temperature control of the impregnation system.

1 INTRODUCTION

Carbon fiber (CF), with its outstanding properties, plays a key role in fiber-reinforced plastics, as it combines high mechanical properties with a low dead weight. As a result, the demand for carbon fibers is increasing by around 10 % annually, of which three-quarters are used for fiber-reinforced plastic (FRP) [1].

In the production of FRP, the pultrusion manufacturing process has the highest growth rate with currently 5 % [2]. The market demands highly rigid components with simultaneously low dead weight, which are to be manufactured with a high degree of automation and high reproducibility. Both requirements are conditionally fulfilled by the conventional pultrusion process, in which the fibers are impregnated with the matrix system via an open impregnation bath. For impregnation, using an open impregnation bath, the choice is limited to matrix systems with a long processing time at room temperature [3].

However, especially with carbon fibers, great challenges are encountered in the complete and uniform impregnation of the fibers by means of closed injection pultrusion [4, 5]. An incomplete and uneven impregnation leads to reduced and strongly scattered mechanical properties [6, 7].

This can possibly be remedied by integrating power ultrasonic (US) into the closed impregnation

chamber. US has many fields of application such as mixing, homogenizing, dispersing and is used in numerous industries (biology, chemistry, ...) [8–10].

The mentioned fields of application of US are all based on the effect of cavitation. Cavitation occurs at sufficiently high sound pressures where the tensile strength of the liquid is exceeded. In 1907, Rayleigh was the first to define the term "cavitation", which is primarily caused by dissolved gases in liquids, interfaces or micro cracks [11, 12]. Cavitation can be used to modify the fiber surface so that a higher oxygen content is achieved with CF [13, 14]. The following effects should be achieved by sonication of the matrix: the surface tension decreases [15], a better mixing is achieved [16], the degree of curing increases [17] and the viscosity is reduced [18, 19]. Publications also show positive effects with CF. After the ultrasonic treatment of CF, the impregnation performance should increase [20–22], the pore content should decrease [23–25] and the strength should be increased by an improved fiber matrix adhesion [14, 15].

The motivation of the work is to integrate the positive properties into the pultrusion in order to improve the impregnation performance of the closed injection pultrusion. The impregnation describes the wetting and impregnation of the fiber package with the matrix system. By means of high-frequency oscillation, the fibers and matrix are moving fast. This should ensure a complete impregnation of even strongly anisotropic carbon fiber packages and the matrix system.

2 MATERIALS AND METHODS

The influence of US on the process is investigated by modification of an existing pultrusion die. The US is integrated into the injection and impregnation chamber (II-chamber). The parameters to be investigated are divided into process parameters (pull-off force, pressure build-up and pull-off speed) and mechanical parameters (bending strength and stiffness (3-point bending), interlaminar shear strength (ILSS) and microscopy).

2.1 Materials

The epoxy resin system Biresin®CR141 (Sika, Germany) was used as matrix system. The composition is summarized in Table 1. The GF is the SE 3030 with 4800 tex (3B, Belgium) and the CF is the CT50-4.0/240-E100 with 50k (SGL Carbon SE, Germany).

Category	Name	Company	Parts
Resin	Biresin®CR141	Sika	100
Hardener	Biresin®CH141	Sika	90
Accelerator	Biresin®CA141	Sika	2
Internal mold release	Chemlease® IC25	ChemTrend	6

Table 1: Epoxy resin system composition

2.2 Methods

The process tests are carried out with a pultrusion line Pultrex type Px500-10T with a maximum pull-off force of 10 tf. The following interfaces are available for process monitoring: 12x temperature sensors; 6x regulated heating zones; 1x force sensor for determining the pull-off force; 4x analog inputs for the connection of external pressure sensors.

The matrix system is injected through a material pressure vessel. The matrix system can be injected over a pressure range of up to 8 bar with a resolution of 0.2 bar. An ultrasonic processor of the Hielscher company type UIP1000hdT with a working power of 1000 Watt is used for the examination. The operating frequency is in the range of 19 – 20 kHz with a maximum amplitude of the surge transducer of 25 µm.

The aim of the II-chamber is to examine the US in the pultrusion process - in particular by means of closed injection pultrusion. For this purpose, the US is implemented in a II-chamber. Figure 1 shows the developed tool system consisting of an II-chamber with mounted US converter and screwed on forming tool. Starting point is a forming tool. This produces a flat profile with the dimensions

60x5 mm². The choice for the flat profile results on the one hand from the thickness of 5 mm – which is difficult to process with a pure unidirectional reinforcement – by means of closed impregnation. On the other hand, with a flat profile, test specimens can be cut out and analyzed with reasonable effort.

Figure 1: Tool system with integrated US converter

The five parameters to be examined are as follows: Location of the US excitation (6 positions), US amplitude (6 – 60 μm), temperature (20 – 70 °C) and the geometry of the II-chamber (conical [26], teardrop [27]). The schematic implementation of the II-chamber, as shown in Figure 2, results from the control and test variables mentioned. A total of six slide-in modules are provided at the top and bottom, which permit variable positioning of the US, the injection and the pressure measurement. The sonotrode (40x20 mm²) is mounted transversely to the pull-off [28] direction, to ensure that 40 mm of the 60 mm wide profile are centrally sonicated. By means of integrated drilling channels, the II-chamber can be tempered to a desired temperature of 20 – 70 °C, using water as heating medium. The internal geometry of the II-chamber corresponds to a conical II-chamber, with an inlet angle of 2x1.4°. The inlet angle is oriented to already manufactured II-chambers at the Fraunhofer IGCV. By using inserts, the conical inner geometry can be changed into a teardrop shape with a height of 5.6 mm in the inlet area.

Figure 2: Schematic representation of the II-chamber

Figure 3 shows the final assembly. After the forming tool has a homogeneous temperature distribution of 180 °C, the test begins by injecting the matrix system into the II-chamber. As soon as the II-chamber is filled, the fiber strand is drawn continuously at a pull-off speed of 0.3 m/min.

Between each parameter setting, a 3 m profile is produced so that the entire system has reached steady-state. Samples are then taken from each setting 4x1 m and the pull-off force, pressures, temperatures and US power are recorded. If necessary, a thermocouple is pulled through the tool system after the last sample.

Figure 3: Mounted II-chamber and forming tool

The 3 point bending test is performed according to DIN EN ISO 14125 and the ILSS according to DIN EN 2377.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The results are presented and discussed separately according to the results for GF and CF in the following section. The name of the tests is always given according to the following nomenclature:

- Name: <Impregnation type>_<Amplitude>_<Pull-off speed>_<Tempering>
 - Impregnation type: xxx stands for open impregnating bath. TI1 - BI2 is the position of the US sonotrode in the II-chamber. The impregnation then takes place within the II-chamber.
 - Amplitude: US amplitude given in μm
 - Pull-off speed: Pull-off speed given in m/min
 - Tempering: xx stands for room temperature, which is within a range of 20 – 30 °C. If the temperature control is active, the temperature is given in °C.

3.1 Investigation results for GF with a conical II-chamber

The results are discussed in the following order: Temperature development; pull-off force and pressures; 3-point bending; ILSS.

Temperature development: The TI1 experiment with an amplitude of 6.6 μm reaches a maximum temperature of 65 °C within the II-chamber (see Figure 4). Experiment TI1_13.2_0.4 shows that a lot of energy can be introduced very quickly by US. A maximum temperature of 280 °C is measured here. The position of the measured temperature is directly below the ultrasonic sonotrode. In the test TI2_26.3_0.3 the maximum measured temperature is 160 °C. This is significantly lower than in the TI1_13.2_0.4 test, although the amplitude is twice as high. The hydraulic pressure increases in the x-direction in the II-chamber. Thus the pressure at position TI1 is higher than at position TI2. In summary, the results from the resin characterization are confirmed. The highest temperature increase is achieved by a high amplitude and pressure

Pull-off force and pressures: In test TI2_00.0_0.3 the pull-off force is around 9 kN (Figure 4). Pressures are at 24 bar at BI1 and 2 bar at BI2. The test shows the initial situation without US. It can be seen that the pressure increases in the x-direction within the II-chamber (already mentioned in the section on temperature development). With increasing compaction of the fiber package, the flow resistance and thus the pressure build-up increases. test TI2_13.2_0.3 shows an important development: After the ultrasound has been switched on, the pull-off force drops to 6 kN (-30 %), the pressure at position BI1 to 7 bar (-70 %) and at position BI2 to below 2 bar (-20 %). The trend continues when the amplitude is increased from 13.2 to 26.3 μm . A further drop in the measured values can be seen. Overall, the test series results in a reduction of the pull-off force by 65 %, for pressure at position BI1 by 80 % and for pressure at position BI2 by approx. 100 %. In summary, US can achieve a considerable reduction of hydraulic pressure within the II-chamber. The reduction of pressure directly results in a reduction of the pull-off force.

Figure 4: Temperature development (left), pull-off force and chamber pressure (right)

ILSS: The test xxx_00.0_0.3 serves as a reference. The impregnation was carried out by an open impregnating bath. The shear strength is in the range of 70 MPa (see Figure 5). All tests with impregnation via the II-chamber do not reach the value of 70 MPa, but lie in the range from 59 to 65 MPa. However, it can be seen that the sonication from below has a positive influence on the strength in comparison with conventional II-chambers. Test BI2_13.2_0.3 has reached the highest value with 65 MPa and shows the lowest scatter. The test TI1_13.2_0.4 shows a peak value of 280 °C in the temperature measurement. However, with a shear strength of 59 MPa, the value is hardly lower than in the other tests with the II-chamber. In summary, it can be seen that the greatest positive effect is achieved by sonication from below. In addition, a temperature increase due to the US has no negative effect on the shear strength.

3-point bending: The test xxx_00.0_0.3 serves as reference. The bending strength is in the range of 1650 MPa (see Figure 5). All tests with impregnation via the II-chamber have a flexural strength of 1400 to 1550 MPa and do not reach the reference value. Comparable to the ILSS test, sonication from below improves the properties here as well. Compared to the conventional II-chamber (TI2_00.0_0.3) the bending strength increases from 1475 to 1550 MPa with reduced scattering. The tests TI1_13.2_0.4 and TI2_26.3_0.3 show the lowest bending strength values of 1300 and 1375 MPa with increased scattering. TI1_13.2_0.4 in particular shows that the reduced properties are due to fiber damage. In summary, it can be said that sonication from below has the greatest positive effect. The properties are better (+5 %) than with the conventional II-chamber. Compared to the open impregnating bath, however, the properties are worse (-6 %). In order to avoid fiber damage, the amplitude is limited upwards.

Figure 5: ILSS (left), 3-point bending (right) of GF

3.2 Investigation results for CF

The results are discussed in the following order: Pressure development; ILSS; 3-point bending; degree of impregnation.

Pressure development: Figure 6 shows the pressure development for the teardrop (left) and conical II-chamber (right). The US amplitude and temperature were varied during the experiments. If no temperature control and US amplitude are activated, the output pressure for the teardrop II-chamber is around 3 bar. By increasing the US amplitude, pressure increases to about 5 bar. The opposite is the case when the temperature is increased from 20 °C to 70 °C. The pressure in the US chamber increases to about 5 bar. Then, at a US amplitude of 0.0 μm, pressure is reduced from 3 bar to less than 1 bar. After the US has been activated, pressure rises to over 7 bar.

Results are different with the conical II-chamber. Here, pressure decreases both with activation of the US amplitude and temperature control. The influence of temperature control is higher than that of the US amplitude. In summary, the result can be interpreted as follows: there is no completely impregnated fiber package with the teardrop II-chamber. Due to the US amplitude and temperature control, the viscosity of the matrix is reduced so that the fiber package is impregnated better. Consequently, the measured chamber pressure also increases with a better impregnation. The conical II-chamber has an almost completely impregnated fiber package. The viscosity of the matrix is reduced by means of the US amplitude and temperature control. Excess matrix – which flows back at the tool inlet – builds up a correspondingly lower hydraulic pressure.

ILSS: Mechanical investigations (ILSS and 3-point bending) were carried out only with components manufactured by means of conical II-chamber. The parts produced with the teardrop II-chamber were not completely impregnated, so that a mechanical examination would not have produced reasonable results. Test xxx_00,0_0,3_xx serves as a reference in which the impregnation was carried out by an open impregnation bath. The shear strength is in a range of about 75 MPa (see Figure 7). The value is not reached if the impregnation is carried out by a conical II-chamber. The range of values is 65 – 70 MPa. The tests with US amplitude show that no significant influence by US is discernible. In addition, it is shown that the dispersion is higher when impregnating with the II-chamber than with the open impregnating bath.

Figure 6: II-chamber pressure as a function of geometry: teardrop (left), conical (right)

3-point bedding: The test xxx_00.0_0.3 serves as reference. The flexural strength is in the range of 1400 MPa (see Figure 7) and thus about 250 MPa below the reference sample from GF. All tests with impregnation via the II-chamber have a flexural strength of 1200 – 1250 MPa and are thus about 200 MPa below the reference value. It has been shown that the US amplitude at different positions (BI1 and BI2) slightly increases strength and also slightly reduces dispersion. However, the same effect can also be achieved if the II-chamber is tempered to 70 °C (BI2_00.0_0.3_70). In summary, the US results in only a slight improvement of the mechanical properties. The main effect will probably be temperature control, since similar mechanical properties are achieved by temperature control of the II-chamber.

Figure 7: ILSS (left), 3-point bending (right) of CF

Degree of impregnation: As already mentioned in the ILSS section, no complete impregnation of the components could be achieved using the teardrop II-chamber. For this reason, the degree of impregnation was introduced as the study parameter. The impregnated area is compared optically in relation to the total profile area. Figure 8 shows the test ranges without active temperature control of the II-chamber on the left side and the test series with active temperature control on the right side. Without temperature control, the degree of impregnation can also be improved by increasing the US amplitude. Starting with approximately 80 % impregnated area, the impregnation can be improved to almost 100 % by increasing the US amplitude to up to 15.1 μm. Complete impregnation could not be achieved as stable production was still not possible. In addition, it must be mentioned that the first fiber damage is already visible on the surface at 15.1 μm. The results of the test series with active temperature control are shown in Figure 8 on the right-hand side. One can tell that the initial level of

around 40 % is significantly lower than in the BI2_00.0_0.3_xx test with 80 %. This shows that the results of one test series are only comparable within that series but not with other test series. Within the test series with active temperature control, the impregnation improves with increasing US amplitude and temperature. The effect of temperature control is higher than that of US amplitude. In summary, the US amplitude has a positive effect on impregnation (+100 %). However, the amount of amplitude is limited due to the resulting fiber damage. A similar effect can be achieved by means of temperature control (+100 %).

Figure 8: Degree of impregnation as a function of amplitude and temperature

4 CONCLUSION AND OUTLOOK

This study examined the influence of power ultrasonic to the closed injection pultrusion process.

The process characterization shows that US can significantly reduce important process variables such as pressure and pull-off force. US enables the introduction of heat energy into the system very quickly and intensively. On the other hand, the mechanical characteristics show that the properties of the reference cannot be achieved with an open bath. Compared to the conventional II-chamber, the strength of GF can be increased by up to 5 %. The picture for CF is mixed. In the case of the conical II-chamber, no significant increase in the mechanical characteristic values could be achieved in comparison with the conventional II-chamber. The results for the teardrop II-chamber, on the other hand, are more promising. Here, the degree of impregnation could be increased to almost 100 % with US. Despite good impregnation, stable component production is still not possible. The high degree of saturation can also be achieved by active temperature control of the II-chamber to 70 °C.

The influence of US on matrix viscosity and fiber damage will be investigated in more detail in further investigations.

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